

The Source of Genius – Does a Machine “Genius” Exist?¹

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In my essay, I will examine Immanuel Kant’s concept of genius to explore whether a “machine genius” could exist alongside human genius.

In addressing the following questions:

- What is fine art?
- Can the creation of art be defined by rules?
- Can art be taught or learned?
- Who can be considered a genius?
- Are products generated by artificial intelligence considered fine art?
- Can genius be produced or taught?

I explore and analyze problems concerning the origins of genius, what is defined as fine art in Kantian terms, how these two concepts are interconnected, and whether genius can be learned or replicated, thereby questioning if it can be produced in the form of machines.

In Kantian aesthetics, the relationship between nature and art is also of key importance in the discussion of genius: “A natural beauty is a *beautiful thing*; artistic beauty is a *beautiful presentation* of a thing.” (CPJ: 48 §)² In my essay, based on Kant’s concept of genius and fine art, I will argue that if we conceive machines as tools in the creative process, serving as embodiments of the creation of artworks, then genius remains a human attribute, and what is created with the machine can indeed be considered fine art. Conversely, if we regard machines as independent creators, they may act as mimics of genius (in an artistic sense), producing the appearance of genius through behavioral mimicry. Although capable of numerous variations that seem to surpass human creativity, this belongs more to the realm of machine “creativity” rather than genius. Accordingly, their output cannot be classified as fine art, as only the genius is capable of producing it. The cultural archive from which machines draw is already nourished by works created by geniuses, and it does not fit Kant’s concept of a “model” because it does not serve as a model to be followed but

¹The essay was published in Hungarian in the 2024/3 issue (Volume 6) of *Cultural Science Review* on January 24, 2024, Hungary.

https://kpvk.pte.hu/sites/kpvk.pte.hu/files/attached/page/kulturatudomanyi_szemle_2024_3_1_verz.pdf

²“Eine Naturschönheit ist ein *schönes Ding*; die Kunstschönheit ist eine *schöne Vorstellung* von einem Dinge.” (KU: 48 §)

instead generates combinations (much like human copying is not considered genius). Furthermore, the effectiveness of this output is attributed to the progress of science, which, according to Kant, does not fall under the category of genius. Thus, we can create creative agents in our own image, who might even surpass our capabilities. However, their works cannot be regarded as original in terms of uniqueness. Furthermore, given the absence of rules governing the creation of artworks due to the lack of conceptual frameworks, we cannot attribute the source of genius to machine models. According to Kant: "...he himself does not know how he came by the ideas for it; nor is it in his power [Gewalt] to devise such products at his pleasure, or by following a plan, and to communicate [his procedure] to others in precepts that would enable them to bring about like products." (CPJ: 46 §)³ Furthermore, "Genius is the innate mental predisposition (ingenium) through which nature gives the rule to art." (CPJ: 46 §)⁴ Without taste, imagination, understanding, and spirit, the concept of genius cannot be discussed. These qualities are innate to humans through natural processes, whereas a machine "borrows" this "knowledge" from human sources. "Hence fine art would seem to require imagination, understanding, spirit, and taste." (CPJ: 50 §)⁵

In terminological terms, the concept of genius originates from the Latin word *genius*, which refers to a guardian spirit present from birth, an innate ability or inclination that later evolved to signify "exceptional natural talent." The root of "genius" is the Latin *gignere* ("to beget"), as well as the Greek *genna* ("γέννά") and its variations, all derived from the Indo-European root *genh-* ("to beget"). This etymology is closely related to origins, nature, and creation.

Kant defines the attributes necessary for genius and how genius operates as follows:

- Natural: It is an inherent quality (mental endowment), created by the nature of the subject.
- Original: It cannot be acquired through rules or replicated; it is unique.
- Exemplary: It serves as a model for imitation but is not itself imitable (emblematic).
- Guiding Spirit: A guiding spirit is required for the generation of ideas.
- Characterized by Freedom: It operates independently of rules.
- Resulting from Imagination, Understanding, and Taste: Genius emerges from the interplay of these faculties.

³"...selbst nicht weiß, wie sich in ihm die Ideen dazu herbei finden, auch es nicht in seiner Gewalt hat, dergleichen nach Belieben oder planmäßig auszudenken und anderen in solchen Vorschriften mitzuteilen, die sie in Stand setzen, gleichmäßige Produkte hervorzubringen." (KU: 46 §)

⁴"*Genie* ist die angeborene Gemütsanlage (ingenium), *durch welche* die Natur der Kunst die Regel gibt." (KU: 46 §)

⁵"Zur schönen Kunst würden also *Einbildungskraft, Verstand, Geist* und *Geschmack* erforderlich sein" (KU: 50 §)

The process by which genius brings forth a work of art in the Kantian sense is as follows: nature – material – experience – spirit – imagination – aesthetic idea – practice – form – artwork. However, a rule cannot be predetermined for this process; understanding the mode of formation requires abstracting backward from the creation itself. During this process, what emerges within the genius is the aesthetic idea, which Kant defines as the imagination, when set into productive cognitive motion, activating the capability of conceptual ideas. Thanks to the imagination, it is possible to represent the transcendental in art. Kant identifies poetry as a prime example of the grandeur of aesthetic ideas. Through aesthetic attributes, imagination can be expressed in such a way that these attributes, as representations of imagination, appear as consequences connected to the concept, serving to enliven the mind. For instance, sensations that prompt deeper contemplation, though not explicitly articulated, as one might condense into a specific linguistic expression. “In a word, an aesthetic idea is a presentation of the imagination which is conjoined with a given concept and is connected, when we use imagination in its freedom, with such a multiplicity of partial presentations that no expression that stands for a determinate concept can be found for it.” (CPJ: 49 §)⁶

In Kant's interpretation, genius is exclusively artistic; thus, achievements in science cannot be classified as genius. Consequently, while an artist can be considered a genius, a scientist cannot. For Kant, science involves following and applying rules, proceeding along a natural path of thought that is learnable. A scientist can be reproduced and taught, but genius is not something that can be learned. Similarly, new trends in art cannot be predicted by rules:

“The reason for this is that Newton could show how he took every one of the steps he had to take in order to get from the first elements of geometry to his great and profound discoveries; he could show this not only to himself but to everyone else as well, in an intuitive[ly clear] way, allowing others to follow. But no Homer or Wieland can show how his ideas, rich in fancy and yet also in thought, arise and meet in his mind; the reason is that he himself does not know, and hence also cannot teach it to anyone else.” (CPJ: 47 §)⁷

⁶“Mit einem Worte, die ästhetische Idee ist eine einem gegebenen Begriffe beigeordnete Vorstellung der Einbildungskraft, welche mit einer solchen Mannigfaltigkeit der Teilvorstellungen in dem freien Gebrauche derselben verbunden ist, dass für sie kein Ausdruck, der einen bestimmten Begriff bezeichnet, gefunden werden kann” (KU: 49 §)

⁷“Die Ursache ist, daß Newton alle seine Schritte, die er von den ersten Elementen der Geometrie an bis zu seinen großen und tiefen Erfindungen zu thun hatte, nicht allein sich selbst, sondern jedem andern ganz anschaulich und zur Nachfolge bestimmt vormachen könnte; kein Homer aber oder Wieland anzeigen kann, wie sich seine

But where does this intellectual ability originate from? According to the approach appearing in antiquity, as presented in Plato's dialogue Ion, the following is stated in the conversation between Socrates and Ion: "You know, none of the epic poets, if they're good, are masters of their subject; they are inspired, possessed, and that is how they utter all those beautiful poems..." {"...the Muse has aroused him..." – Socrates. (Ion: 533e, 534c) Two thousand years later, Schopenhauer defines genius in terms of *perceptive* knowledge, where the genius perceives more profoundly into the world. The works of the genius originate directly from this perception and are oriented towards it:

"...the true nature of genius must lie in the completeness and energy of the knowledge of perception. In accordance with this, we hear described most decidedly as works of genius those which start from, and appeal to, perception, hence those of the plastic and pictorial arts, and then those of poetry which brings about its perceptions through the imagination." {} „The person endowed with talent thinks more rapidly and accurately than do the rest; on the other hand, the genius perceives a world different from them all, though only by looking more deeply into the world that lies before them also, since it presents itself in his mind more objectively, consequently more purely and distinctly.” (Schopenhauer, 1819, 31 §)⁸

Kant asserts that taste is not a productive ability and, as such, is insufficient on its own for genius; however, it is an integral aspect of genius. In the case of fine arts, we are dealing with more than mere judgments of taste. While the aim of pleasant art is to evoke a sense of pleasure, fine art is associated with modes of cognition:

phantasiereichen und doch zugleich gedankenvollen Ideen in seinem Kopfe hervor und zusammen finden, darum weil er es selbst nicht weiß und es also auch keinen andern lehren kann." (KU: 47 §)

⁸“...so muß das Wesen des Genies in der Vollkommenheit und Energie der anschauenden Erkenntniß liegen. Dem entsprechend hören wir als Werke des Genies am entschiedensten solche bezeichnen, welche unmittelbar von der Anschauung ausgehen und an die Anschauung sich wenden, also die der bildenden Künste, und nächst dem die der Poesie, welche ihre Anschauungen durch die Phantasie vermittelt.” {} „Der damit Begabte denkt rascher und richtiger als die Übrigen; das Genie hingegen schaut eine andere Welt an, als sie Alle, wiewohl nur indem es in die auch ihnen vorliegende tiefer hineinschaut, weil sie in seinem Kopfe sich objektiver, mithin reiner und deutlicher darstellt.” (Schopenhauer, 1819, 31§)

“Now, on the other hand, a judgment of taste does deal with objects of sense—though not so as to determine a concept of these objects for the understanding, since it is not a cognitive judgment. Rather, this judgment is a singular intuitive presentation referred to the feeling of pleasure, and hence is only a private judgment; and to this extent its validity would be restricted to the judging individual: The object is an object of liking for me; the same may not apply to others: Everyone has his own taste.”⁹ (CPJ: 57 §)

What aligns with taste may belong to mechanical art. How does fine art distinguish itself from mechanical art? Mechanical art performs the operations necessary for the realization of the object according to the knowledge it has of the subject. „Fine art is the art of genius.”¹⁰ (CPJ: 46 §)

The art of the genius must be both free and mechanical, as mechanical regularity is essential for shaping during execution. Art can be considered akin to play; it is a pleasant activity taken for its own sake, purposeless and free from personal interest. While art is free, craftsmanship, according to Kant, can be classified as applied art, which is burdensome and dependent on external interests. Fine art is natural and inherently purposeful, created by the genius with taste.

In summary, based on Kantian concepts, my conclusion is as follows: The notion of genius is intrinsically linked to the human subject, who is endowed by nature with the faculties of the mind, reason, understanding, imagination, taste, experience and spirit. Consequently, this subject creates fine art purposefully yet freely, striving for perfection. When considering machine genius, we cannot speak of a subject possessing these faculties, as these abilities cannot be learned or created but are inherent to nature. With the advancement of machine learning techniques, we encounter simulations of these capabilities, where the modes of acquiring knowledge and information differ, resulting in a product that is fundamentally distinct and indirectly derived from human knowledge. In the absence of genius, the product created can be likened to applied art or mechanical art. “An aesthetic idea cannot become cognition because it is an *intuition* (of the imagination) for which an adequate concept can never be found.”¹¹ (CPJ: 57§)

⁹“Nun geht das Geschmacksurteil auf Gegenstände der Sinne, aber nicht um einen *Begriff* derselben für den Verstand zu bestimmen; denn es ist kein Erkenntnisurteil. Es ist daher, als auf das Gefühl der Lust bezogene anschauliche einzelne Vorstellung, nur ein Privatteil: und sofern würde es seiner Gültigkeit nach auf das urteilende Individuum allein beschränkt sein: der Gegenstand ist *für mich* ein Gegenstand des Wohlgefallens, für andere mag es sich anders verhalten; – ein jeder hat seinen Geschmack.” (KU: 57§)

¹⁰“Schöne Kunst ist Kunst des Genies.” (KU: 46§)

¹¹“Eine *ästhetische Idee* kann keine Erkenntnis werden, weil sie eine *Anschauung* (der Einbildungskraft) ist, der

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Abbreviations:

CPJ: Critique of Judgment

KU: Kritik der Urteilskraft

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niemals ein Begriff adäquat gefunden werden kann.” (KU: 57§)